

Supplementary Survey Response Report

Design conservatism and embodied carbon: An exploratory survey of structural engineers in Malaysia

Aggregated item-level descriptive survey results

June 2024

Repository note

This supplementary report provides aggregated descriptive results from the survey used to support the associated journal manuscript. It is intended to improve transparency by documenting the questionnaire structure, data screening decisions, valid response counts, frequency distributions and summary statistics. Raw respondent-level data are not included in this report in order to protect participant confidentiality.

Table of Contents

1.0	Introduction	3
2.0	Survey Questions.....	4
3.0	Survey Responses.....	5
3.1	Section 7: Survey Population (8 questions) (Q37-44).....	6
3.2	Section 1 : General Questions (11 questions) (Q1-11).....	12
3.3	Section 2: Loading (8 questions) (Q12-19).....	17
3.4	Section 3: Serviceability (3 questions) (Q20-22).....	27
3.5	Section 4: Design (4 questions) (Q23-26).....	29
3.6	Section 5: Capacity (4 questions) (Q27 to 30).....	32
3.7	Section 6: Design Examples (6 questions) (Q31 to 36).....	35
4.0	Repository suitability note	41

1.0 Introduction

This supplementary survey response report provides aggregated item-level descriptive results from a survey of structural engineering practitioners in Malaysia. The report supports the manuscript titled “Design conservatism and embodied carbon: An exploratory survey of structural engineers in Malaysia”. It documents the questionnaire structure, data screening decisions, valid response counts, frequency distributions and summary statistics used to interpret the survey findings.

The survey examined engineering decision-making, material utilisation, loading assumptions, serviceability considerations, design resistance decisions, capacity limits and design examples. The questionnaire was adapted from the MEICON: Minimising Carbon in Construction, Survey of Structural Engineering, conducted by the University of Cambridge and the University of Bath, UK. MEICON was a research project funded by Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) in grant EP/P033679/1, led by Professor Dr John Orr.

The report presents aggregated descriptive results only. It does not include the raw respondent-level dataset or identifiable participant information. Free-text responses are summarised only at an aggregate level where appropriate, in order to protect respondent confidentiality.

The findings should be interpreted as exploratory and descriptive. The survey was conducted among practitioners in Malaysia and is not intended to provide statistically generalisable estimates for the entire structural engineering profession. The results are therefore best used as supplementary evidence for interpreting reported design practices and material-utilisation-related decision-making.

2.0 Survey Questions

The survey comprised seven sections and 44 questions. All questions were optional; therefore, the valid response count varies across items.

Section 1: General Questions (11 questions)

This section captured baseline information on respondents' design approach and their experience of the relationship between design, construction, and client requirements. The 11 items used a 7-point Likert scale from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 7 = Strongly Agree.

Section 2: Loading (8 questions)

This section included numerical and Likert-scale questions exploring relationships between design loads, perceived real loading in office structures, and possible changes to imposed floor loading.

Section 3: Serviceability (3 questions)

This section asked how often serviceability criteria govern structural design, which serviceability criteria most often govern design, and how frequently respondents would be comfortable allowing selected serviceability limits to be exceeded.

Section 4: Design (4 questions)

This section consisted of four questions relating to realistic design scenarios and the relationship between design resistance and design effect actions. The items included fixed-response, Likert-scale and numerical questions.

Section 5: Capacity (4 questions)

This section included four questions relating to utilisation of structural elements in buildings. The items included one Likert-scale question, two numerical-response questions and one free-text question.

Section 6: Design Examples (6 questions)

This section asked respondents to consider examples from their own work and from wider professional practice. The items included numerical, fixed-response and free-text questions.

Section 7: Population (8 questions)

This section asked about respondents' profession, country, position, role, gender, age and years of professional experience. One additional question asked whether respondents had read the MEICON 2018 report.

3.0 Survey Responses

The survey was administered from 3 November 2023 to 20 April 2024. Invitations were distributed to 485 civil and structural engineering companies and individual practising civil and structural engineers in Malaysia. As recipients may have forwarded the survey invitation, the response rate should be interpreted cautiously. A total of 53 responses was received, of which 50 were retained after screening for descriptive analysis.

Data screening and cleaning

Because the survey targeted structural engineering practice, responses were screened for professional relevance and completeness. Three responses were excluded for the following reasons:

One response was excluded because it was substantially incomplete and did not include profile information needed to verify respondent eligibility.

One response was excluded because the respondent did not provide sufficient information to verify professional suitability.

One response was excluded because the profession stated was outside the target structural engineering population.

After screening, 50 valid responses were retained for descriptive analysis.

Outlier removal (for continuous variables)

For continuous variables, extreme outliers were reviewed on a case-by-case basis using boxplot analysis. Only values identified as extreme outliers were excluded from the relevant item-level descriptive statistics. Exclusions were applied pairwise, meaning that an excluded value for one question did not remove the respondent from all other analyses.

Q14: Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Q15: Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Q16: Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Q17: Three extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Q18: Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Q19: Three extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Q31: Three extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Q34: One extreme outlying value was excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Missing data

Respondents were allowed to skip questions that were not relevant to their practice. Missing data were handled using pairwise exclusion, so each item was analysed using the valid responses available for that question. For string variables, blank responses were recoded as missing data.

3.1 Section 7: Survey Population (8 questions) (Q37-44)

Section 7 was asked at the end of the survey and is presented first to provide an overview of the respondent profile. It includes questions on profession, country, position, role, gender, age and years of professional experience, as well as one question on whether respondents had read the MEICON 2018 report.

3.1.1 Question 37: Your profession (n=50)

Table 1: Your profession

Profession	Frequency	%
Structural Engineer	30	60
Civil Engineer	15	30
Contractor	2	4
Architect	0	0
Other:		
Project Engineer	1	2
Project Manager	1	2
Academic	1	2
Total	50	100

Figure 1: Your profession

Out of 50 valid responses, 30 respondents identified as structural engineers and 15 as civil engineers. The remaining respondents identified themselves in related roles, including contractor, project engineer, project manager and academic.

3.1.2 Question 38: Country (n=49)

Table 2: Country where your office is located

Country	Frequency	%
Malaysia	49	98
Did not answer	1	2
	50	100

The survey was conducted in Malaysia. Forty-nine respondents reported that their office was located in Malaysia, while one respondent did not answer this question.

3.1.3 Question 39: Your position (n=50)

Table 3: Your position

Your Position	Frequency	%
Graduate	20	40
Senior Engineer	16	32
Associate	0	0
Associate Director	0	0
Director	5	10
Executive Officer	4	8
Other:		
Engineer	2	4
Mid-level Junior Engineer	1	2
Project Manager	1	2
Senior Principal	1	2
Total	50	100

The respondent profile included 20 graduate engineers, 16 senior engineers, 5 directors, 4 executive officers and several other professional roles.

Figure 2: Your position

3.1.4 Question 40: Your Role (n=50)

Table 4: Your role

Your Role	Frequency	%
Detailed design	27	54
Concept design	11	22
Feasibility studies	6	12
Pre-design client discussion	6	12
Total	50	100

A total of 27 respondents reported that their main role was detailed design, while 11 reported concept design. Six respondents reported feasibility studies and six reported pre-design client discussions.

Figure 3: Your role

3.1.5 Question 41: What gender do you identify as? (n=50)

Table 5: What gender do you identify as?

Gender	Frequency	%
Male	36	72
Female	9	18
Prefer not to say	4	8
Other: Don't think it is relevant	1	2
Total	50	100

A total of 36 respondents identified as male, nine as female, four preferred not to say, and one selected "Don't think it is relevant".

Figure 4: What gender do you identify as?

3.1.6 Question 42: Your age (n=50)

Table 6: Your age

Age	Frequency	%
16-24	3	6
25-34	28	56
35-44	8	16
45-54	4	8
55-64	6	12
65-74	1	2
85+	0	0
Total	50	100

A total of 28 respondents were in the 25–34 age group, followed by eight respondents in the 35–44 age group.

Figure 5: Your age

3.1.7 Question 43: Total number of years of experience in the profession (n=49)

Table 7: Total number of years of experience in the profession

Experience in profession (years up to)	Frequency	%
2	16	33%
4	4	8%
6	6	12%
8	5	10%
10	3	6%
15	6	12%
20	0	0%
30	4	8%
40	4	8%
50	1	2%
Total	49	100%

Figure 6: Total number of years of experience in the profession

The number of years of experience of the respondents ranged from 0.5 year to 44 years. The average number of years of experience was 10.3 and the standard deviation was 11 years.

3.1.8 Question 44: Did you read the findings of the first Meicon survey, published in 2018? (n=50)

Table 8: Did you read the findings of the first Meicon survey, published in 2018?

Response	Frequency	%
Yes	2	4
No	44	88
Unsure	4	8
Total	50	100

Figure 7: Did you read the findings of the first Meicon survey, published in 2018?

Two respondents reported that they had read the first MEICON survey report, 44 had not read it, and four were unsure.

3.2 Section 1 : General Questions (11 questions) (Q1-11)

Questions 1-11 were based on 7-point Likert Scales ranging from “1. Strongly Disagree” to “7. Strongly Agree” to ask for baseline information on respondent’s approach to design and their experience of the relationship between design, construction, and client. The frequency for each response is shown in the bar charts and median for each question is presented.

3.2.1 Question 1: Maximising material utilisation is a key design criterion for me (n=47)

Figure 8: Maximising material utilisation is a key design criterion for me

The Median of the responses was 6.

3.2.2 Question 2: The material utilisation of each structural element in my designs is normally close to 1.00 (n =49)

Figure : The material utilisation of each structural element in my designs is normally close to 1.00

The Median of the responses was 5.

3.2.3 Question 3: The oversizing of structural elements during initial or concept design stages is normally appropriate (n=49)

Figure 9: The oversizing of structural elements during initial or concept design stages is normally appropriate

The Median of the responses was 5.

3.2.4 Question 4: An easily constructed structure is more valued by the whole design team than a materially efficient structure (n=50)

Figure 10: An easily constructed structure is more valued by the whole design team than a materially efficient structure

The Median of the responses was 5.

3.2.5 Question 5: Reducing the dimensions of structural elements agreed at concept design stage during detailed design is best avoided. (n=50)

Figure 11: Reducing the dimensions of structural elements agreed at concept design stage during detailed design is best avoided.

The Median of the responses was 4.5.

3.2.6 Question 6: The potential for construction errors influences my structural member sizing decisions. (n=50)

Figure 12: The potential for construction errors influences my structural member sizing decisions.

The Median of the responses was 5.

3.2.7 Question 7: I simplify my structural designs to improve constructability. (n= 50)

Figure 13: I simplify my structural designs to improve constructability.

The Median of the responses was 6.

3.2.8 Question 8: My clients or design team normally require me to minimise embodied energy (or embodied carbon, if this is your preferred criterion) (n=49)

Figure 14: My clients or design team normally require me to minimise embodied energy

The Median of the responses was 4.

3.2.9 Question 9: The material utilisation of a structural design is normally presented to clients (n= 50)

Figure 15: The material utilisation of a structural design is normally presented to clients

The Median of the responses was 4.

3.2.10 Question 10. The best way to reduce material consumption is to ensure that structural material utilisation is high. (n=50)

Figure 16: The best way to reduce material consumption is to ensure that structural material utilisation is high.

The Median of the responses was 5.

3.2.11 Question 11: Clients normally insist on low-carbon structural designs. (n=50)

Figure 17: Clients normally insist on low-carbon structural designs.

The Median of the responses was 4.

3.3 Section 2: Loading (8 questions) (Q12-19)

There are 8 questions in this section. Four are numerical questions which explore the relationship between loads chosen at design and the respondent's understanding of real loading in office structures. Two 7-point Likert and two numerical response questions examine how respondents feel about changes in imposed floor loading. The frequency for each response is shown in the bar charts and median for each question is presented.

3.3.1 Question 12: How often do you think that values for imposed vertical floor design loads given in your local design code of practice are appropriate? (n=50)

Figure 18: How often do you think that values for imposed vertical floor design loads given in your local design code of practice are appropriate?

The Median of the responses was 5.

3.3.2 Question 13: In your experience how often are imposed design loads for floor plates decided by the client? (n=50)

Figure 19: In your experience how often are imposed design loads for floor plates decided by the client?

The Median of the responses was 3.

3.3.3 Question 14: Imagine you are designing a new multi-storey office building for a financial services firm in the centre of a city. What CHARACTERISTIC value of imposed vertical floor design load in the office spaces would you use, excluding any allowance for moveable partitions? (n=44)

Figure 20: Imagine you are designing a new multi-storey office building for a financial services firm in the centre of a city. What CHARACTERISTIC value of imposed vertical floor design load in the office spaces would you use, excluding any allowance for moveable partitions? (Responses group by answer, note the irregular horizontal axis)

Figure 21: Imagine you are designing a new multi-storey office building for a financial services firm in the centre of a city. What CHARACTERISTIC value of imposed vertical floor design load in the office spaces would you use, excluding any allowance for moveable partitions? (Histogram)

Figure 22: Imagine you are designing a new multi-storey office building for a financial services firm in the centre of a city. What CHARACTERISTIC value of imposed vertical floor design load in the office spaces would you use, excluding any allowance for moveable partitions? (Boxplot)

The Mean of the responses was 5.02kN/m²

The Median of the responses was 2.50kN/m²

Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

The new Mean is 2.63 kN/m² while the Median remained as 2.50 kN/m²

3.3.4 Question 15: For the same building, what additional CHARACTERISTIC value for moveable partitions would you use? (n=44)

Figure 23: For the same building, what additional CHARACTERISTIC value for moveable partitions would you use? (Responses group by answer, note the irregular horizontal axis)

Figure 24: For the same building, what additional CHARACTERISTIC value for moveable partitions would you use? (Histogram)

Figure 25: For the same building, what additional CHARACTERISTIC value for moveable partitions would you use? (Boxplot)

The Mean of the responses was 2.80kN/m²
 The Median of the responses was 1.00kN/m²

Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

The new mean is 1.39 kN/m² while the median remained as 1.00kN/m²

3.3.5 Question 16. The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the AVERAGE area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (n=44)

Figure 26: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the AVERAGE area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (Responses group by answer, note the irregular horizontal axis)

Figure 27: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the AVERAGE area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (Histogram)

Figure 28: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the AVERAGE area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (Boxplot)

The Mean of the responses was 4.65kN/m²

The Median of the responses was 2.50kN/m²

Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

The new Mean is 2.51 kN/m² while the Median remained as 2.50 kN/m²

3.3.6 Question 17: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the MAXIMUM area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (n=44)

Figure 29: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the MAXIMUM area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (Responses group by answer, note the irregular horizontal axis)

Figure 30: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the MAXIMUM area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (Histogram)

Figure 31: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the MAXIMUM area load on the floor of the office would be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (1st Boxplot Analysis)

The Mean of the responses was 8514.37kN/m²

The Median of the responses was 3.00kN/m²

One extreme outlying value was excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item because it was substantially outside the observed response range and strongly affected the mean.

Further analysis at the 5% trimmed mean, it showed an obvious extreme difference between 8514.37 (mean) and 4.07 (5% trimmed mean - which omit the highest and lowest 5% of total data point). This indicates the presence of extreme outliers.

After the initial exclusion, two further extreme outlying values were identified and excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

Figure 32: The same building is put into service, and is used as an office space for 60 years. What do you think the MAXIMUM area load on the floor of the office would

be, over the life of the structure, as measured during office hours? (2nd Boxplot Analysis)

After removal of the three extreme outlying values, the new mean was 3.35 kN/m² and the median was 3.00 kN/m².

3.3.7 Question Q18: Thinking about your local design code of practice, what percentage change in vertical loading values do you expect to see in the next ten years? (n=42)

Figure 33: Thinking about your local design code of practice, what percentage change in vertical loading values do you expect to see in the next ten years?

Figure 34: Thinking about your local design code of practice, what percentage change in vertical loading values do you expect to see in the next ten years? (Boxplot)

The Mean of the responses was 9.62%
 The Median of the responses was 0%

Two extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

After removal of the extreme outlying values, the new mean was 3.85% while the median remained as 0%.

3.3.8 Question Q19: Imagine you are solely responsible for rewriting your local structural design code. What percentage changes, if any, in imposed design loading would you introduce? (n=42)

Figure 35: Imagine you are solely responsible for rewriting your local structural design code. What percentage changes, if any, in imposed design loading would you introduce?

Figure 36: Imagine you are solely responsible for rewriting your local structural design code. What percentage changes, if any, in imposed design loading would you introduce? (Boxplot)

The Mean of the responses was 7.58%
 The Median of the responses was 0%

Three extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

After removal of the extreme outlying values, the new mean was 2.91% while the median remained as 0%.

3.4 Section 3: Serviceability (3 questions) (Q20-22)

This section consisted of one question with 7-point Likert scale, one matrix response and one given list response. The questions asked about how often and which serviceability criteria govern designs, along with how often the respondent would allow such criteria to be exceeded.

3.4.1 Question 20: In your experience, how often does the serviceability limit state govern the size of structural elements? (n=48)

Figure 37: In your experience, how often does the serviceability limit state govern the size of structural elements?

The Median of the responses was 5.

3.4.2 Q21. In your experience, which of the following SLS criteria most often governs the design of structural elements in buildings?

Figure 38: In your experience, which of the following SLS criteria most often governs the design of structural elements in buildings?

3.4.3 Question 22: How frequently would you be comfortable with allowing the following structural serviceability limits to be exceeded in an office building throughout its lifetime?

Figure 39: How frequently would you be comfortable with allowing the following structural serviceability limits to be exceeded in an office building throughout its lifetime?

3.5 Section 4: Design (4 questions) (Q23-26)

There are two questions in this section with given text response, one on 7- point Likert scale and one numerical response relating to realistic design scenarios and focus on how relationship between design resistance and design effect actions.

3.5.1 Question 23: You are asked to design the floor plate in a multi-storey building. Which one of the following has the biggest influence on your final design. (n=50)

Figure 40: You are asked to design the floor plate in a multi-storey building. Which one of the following has the biggest influence on your final design.

3.5.2 Question 24: Imagine you are undertaking the detailed design of a flexurally dominated floor beam. The flexural design effect of the actions (“Ed”) on the beam at mid-span is 200kNm (including partial factors). The beam is to be a fabricated steel section. What value for the flexural design resistance (“Rd”) of the beam at mid-span (including partial factors) would you choose? (n=37)

Figure 41: Imagine you are undertaking the detailed design of a flexurally dominated floor beam. The flexural design effect of the actions (“Ed”) on the beam at mid-span is 200kNm (including partial factors). The beam is to be a fabricated steel section. What value for the flexural design resistance (“Rd”) of the beam at mid-span (including partial factors) would you choose?

The Mean of the responses was 231.62kNm

The Median of the responses was 220kNm

Two responses had value of less than 200kNm (80 kNm and 180 kNm), which should be excluded since it is non-compliance with design.

After excluding these two responses, the new Mean was 237.43kNm and the Median was 225 kNm.

3.5.3 Question 25: Thinking about your professional practice, how frequently do elements in your completed structural designs have a design resistance that is EQUAL to the design effect of actions on the element? (n=47)

Figure 42: Thinking about your professional practice, how frequently do elements in your completed structural designs have a design resistance that is EQUAL to the design effect of actions on the element?

The Median of the responses was 3.

3.5.4 Question 26: Thinking about your professional practice, which of the following would be the prime reason for an element to have a design resistance that is greater than the design effect of the actions on the element? (n = 46)

Table 9: Thinking about your professional practice, which of the following would be the prime reason for an element to have a design resistance that is greater than the design effect of the actions on the element?

Response	Frequency	%
The span, loading, or layout might change before construction.	11	23.9
I am uncomfortable with the design effect of the actions being equal to the design resistance of the element.	12	26.1
I don't trust the factors of safety in design codes	0	0
I like to build in a bit of spare capacity just in case.	13	28.3
The building might change use later in its life.	5	10.9
<u>Others:</u>		
Allow for site tolerance (site not construct 100% according to dwgs)	1	2.2
Critical element where failure may be of huge consequences	1	2.2
Follow code and control construction quality	1	2.2
Poor workmanship	1	2.2
Site implementation	1	2.2
Total	46	100

3.6 Section 5: Capacity (4 questions) (Q27 to 30)

This section consisted of four questions relating utilisation of structural elements in buildings. There were one questions with 7-point Likert scale, 2 with numerical response and one required free text response.

3.6.1 Question 27: How feasible do you think it would be to introduce into design codes a limit on how much greater the Design Resistance of a structural element could be as compared to its required capacity? This would prohibit engineers from designing elements with a capacity greater than this upper limit. (n=46)

Figure 43: How feasible do you think it would be to introduce into design codes a limit on how much greater the Design Resistance of a structural element could be as compared to its required capacity? This would prohibit engineers from designing elements with a capacity greater than this upper limit.

The Median of the responses was 4.

3.6.2 Question 28: Imagine that such a limit is introduced into a design code. The Design value of resistance ("R_d") for each element must be greater than the Design effect of the action ("E_d") AND less than "Beta" multiplied by "E_d", where "Beta" is a number ≥ 1.000. This relationship is shown in the equation below. What value of "Beta" would you be happy, as a structural designer, to see in a design code? (n=35)

$$E_d \leq R_d \leq \beta E_d$$

E_d = Design effect of action

R_d = Design value of resistance

$$\beta \geq 1.00$$

Figure 43: Imagine that such a limit is introduced into a design code. The Design value of resistance ("Rd") for each element must be greater than the Design effect of the action ("Ed") AND less than "Beta" multiplied by "Ed", where "Beta" is a number ≥ 1.000 . This relationship is shown in the equation below. What value of "Beta" would you be happy, as a structural designer, to see in a design code?

The Median of the responses was 1.25.

3.6.3 Question 29: What might the unintended consequences of a limit to the design value of resistance relative to the design effect of the actions be, in your opinion? (n=32)

This question collected free text response with 32 answers. They are classified according to the categories in the following table:

Table 10: What might the unintended consequences of a limit to the design value of resistance relative to the design effect of the actions be, in your opinion?

Category	Frequency	%
Limit innovation/design/aesthetic	7	22%
Structural failure/integrity	6	19%
Either overdesign or under-design	2	6%
Limit future use of building	2	6%
None	7	22%
Other	8	25%
Total	32	100%

3.6.4 Question 30: Imagine instead that an average material utilisation across all structural elements is introduced as a codified design requirement. What minimum value of material utilisation should be achieved by structural designers? (n=37)

Figure 44: Imagine instead that an average material utilisation across all structural elements is introduced as a codified design requirement. What minimum value of material utilisation should be achieved by structural designers? (Responses group by answer, note the irregular horizontal axis)

Figure 45: Imagine instead that an average material utilisation across all structural elements is introduced as a codified design requirement. What minimum value of material utilisation should be achieved by structural designers? (Histogram)

The Mean of the responses was 0.82.
The Median of the responses was 0.80.

3.7 Section 6: Design Examples (6 questions) (Q31 to 36)

There were six questions in this sections which ask respondents to think of their own work, and work of others in their profession where examples of designs were explored. Three questions required numerical response, one response with given text and 2 responses required free text.

3.7.1 Question 31: How deep (in mm) would you expect a two-way spanning flat slab in an inner-city office building to be, if the column spacing below it is 7m x 7m? (n= 41)

Figure 46: How deep (in mm) would you expect a two-way spanning flat slab in an inner-city office building to be, if the column spacing below it is 7m x 7m? (Responses group by answer, note the irregular horizontal axis)

Figure 47: How deep (in mm) would you expect a two-way spanning flat slab in an inner-city office building to be, if the column spacing below it is 7m x 7m? (Histogram)

Figure 48: How deep (in mm) would you expect a two-way spanning flat slab in an inner-city office building to be, if the column spacing below it is 7m x 7m? (Boxplot)

The Mean of the responses was 385.61mm

The Median of the responses was 250mm

Three extreme outlying values were excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

After removing the outliers, the new mean was 224.47 mm and the median was 237.5 mm.

3.7.2 Question 32: Imagine you are designing the steel beams in a floor plate of the multi-storey office building shown below. The floor plate is repeated multiple times. There are a large number of beams with varying spans. The floor load is constant across the area. Thinking about the beams only, approximately how many sets of calculations would you probably undertake to size the beams across the floor plate? (n=42)

Figure 49: Imagine you are designing the steel beams in a floor plate of the multi-storey office building shown below. The floor plate is repeated multiple times. There are a large number of beams with varying spans. The floor load is constant across the area. Thinking about the beams only, approximately how many sets of calculations would you probably undertake to size the beams across the floor plate?

The Mean of the responses was 26.45
 The Median of the responses was 10

3.7.3 Question 33: Please provide a short justification for your decision (relating to Q32). (n = 39)

Free text responses were grouped according to categories as shown in the following table:

Table 11: Please provide a short justification for your decision (relating to Q32)

Category	Frequency	%
Grouping/Rationalisation	18	46.2
Ease of construction	8	20.5
Economic Design/Save construction cost	5	12.8
Save design/calculation time	3	7.7
Connection	1	2.6
Other	4	10.2
Total	39	100

3.7.4 Question 34: Thinking about your experience of the structural engineering profession more generally, how many different section depths would you expect to see in the as-built structure, regardless of the number of calculations performed? (n = 38)

Figure 50: Thinking about your experience of the structural engineering profession more generally, how many different section depths would you expect to see in the as-built structure, regardless of the number of calculations performed? (Responses group by answer, note the irregular horizontal axis)

Figure 51: Thinking about your experience of the structural engineering profession more generally, how many different section depths would you expect to see in the as-built structure, regardless of the number of calculations performed? (Histogram)

The Mean of the responses was 15.8

The Median of the responses was 5

One extreme outlying value was excluded from the descriptive statistics for this item.

The new Mean is 9.73 while the Median remained as 5.

3.7.5 Question 35: Imagine you are the structural designer for your OWN house. Would your approach to assumed loads and individual sizing of members be any different from your day-to-day professional role? (n =49)

Table 12: Imagine you are the structural designer for your OWN house. Would your approach to assumed loads and individual sizing of members be any different from your day-to-day professional role?

Response	Frequency	%
No	33	67.3
Yes	16	32.7
Total	49	100

Figure 52: Imagine you are the structural designer for your OWN house. Would your approach to assumed loads and individual sizing of members be any different from your day-to-day professional role?

3.7.6 Question 36: Please provide examples of what you might assume or do differently in the design of your own house. (n = 13)

Table 13: Please provide examples of what you might assume or do differently in the design of your own house.

Category	Frequency	%
Greater certainty	2	15
Simplier /lighter design	2	15
Greater customisation	1	7.6
Lower utilisation	1	7.6
Control of loading	1	7.6
Higher utilisation	1	7.6
None	1	7.6
Other	4	30.8
Total	13	100

4.0 Repository suitability note

This supplementary report provides item-level descriptive results to support transparency in the reporting of the survey findings. Interpretation and discussion of the findings are provided in the associated manuscript. This report therefore presents aggregated response distributions and summary statistics only, without additional analytical interpretation.